

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF ISOMERIC OXIMES. PART I. MOLECULAR
CONDUCTIVITIES IN LIQUID SULPHUR DIOXIDE OF
ISOMERIC ALDOXIMES

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Solutions of oximes in liquid sulphur dioxide gave measurable conductivities. The β -aldoximes in all cases gave higher conductivities than α -aldoximes. Hence by extension of Ostwald's rule regarding ethylenic acids to the aldoximes, the β -forms should be 'anti' and the α -form, 'syn'. These configurations are in agreement with the observations of Beckmann and Meisenheimer.

The object of this work was to seek relation, if any, between configurations and electrical conductivities of isomeric oximes. Brady and Goldstein (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1918) observed conductivities of sodium salts of isomeric aldoximes in aqueous solutions and determined indirectly the dissociation constants K_a of aldoximes from the relations

$$\Lambda_{\text{obs}} = (1-x)\Lambda_0 + x\Lambda_{\text{NaOH}} \qquad K_h = \frac{x^2}{(1-x)v} \qquad K_a = \frac{K_w}{K_h}$$

where Λ_{obs} is the observed conductivity of the sodium salt of an oxime at dilution v , x is the degree of hydrolysis, Λ_0 is the conductivity of the unhydrolysed salt, Λ_{NaOH} is the conductivity of caustic soda and K_w , K_a and K_h are dissociation constant of water, dissociation constant of the oxime and hydrolysis constant of the sodium salt of the oxime respectively. They have shown that in every case of isomeric oximes they observed, the dissociation constant of the α^* form was greater than that of the β -form.

The authors have not given the values of Λ_{obs} , but it may be assumed that these are related to K_a . They prepared solutions of sodium salts by dissolving oximes in calculated quantity of pure aqueous caustic soda.

We prepared sodium salts by adding to an alcoholic solution of an oxime, equivalent amount of sodium dissolved in alcohol and precipitating by addition of ether (Beckmann, *Ber.* 1889, 22, 434; Goldschmidt and Röder, *Ber.*, 1895, 28 2013). Conductivity measurements of the sodium salts of oximes, thus prepared, revealed that whereas in the case of benzaldoxime the sodium salt of α -form has higher conductivity than that of the β -form, opposite is the case with *m*-nitrobenzaloxime. We felt therefore the need of direct comparison of the conductivities of oximes themselves.

On account of their very small solubility and poor ionisation in water, conductivities of oximes in aqueous solutions are inconvenient for comparison. Solutions in non-aqueous solvents like pure acetic acid and nitrobenzene gave very feeble conductivities. The oximes were, however, found to dissolve in liquid sulphur dioxide and these solutions gave measurable conductivities. However, on account of their limited solubility in this solvent and also owing to the difficulty of maintaining constant temperature (-18° in our experiments) for a long period we could vary dilutions only within a limited range.

In all cases of isomeric oximes studied we found the molecular conductivity of the β -form higher throughout than that of α -form. Owing, however, to experimental

* The terms 'syn' and 'anti' are avoided because the applications of these configurations to the isomeric forms is the subject of discussion.

difficulties exactly equal dilutions of the two forms could not be obtained for comparison of conductivities. But as will be clear from the tables, when the dilutions of the two forms are more or less equal, the β -form has a much higher conductivity than α -form. Such values of conductivities are shown by asterisks in the tables.

The α -forms were obtained by oximation of aldehydes in alkaline medium, while the β -forms were prepared from the corresponding α -forms through the hydrochlorides or by exposure of the α -form in benzene solution to sunlight. In the case of cinnamic aldehyde, oximation in alkaline medium gave only the β -form and not a mixture of the α - and β -forms as described by Brady and Choksi (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 947). With furfuraldehyde in alkaline medium Brady and Goldstein (*ibid.*, 1927, 195) obtained α -aldoxime. They observed that if their conditions are not carefully followed inseparable mixture of α - and β -forms is obtained. We obtained the pure β -form instead of the α -form or the mixture. Its high molecular conductivity is in conformity with the behaviour of β -oximes (Table VI).

In the case of *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde we found that of the two α -forms described in literature, the one melting at 60° (Goldschmidt, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2790) gave low values of molecular conductivity like other α -oximes, but the other melting at 48° (Westenberger, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2994) behaved like β -oximes giving high values for molecular conductivities. These values were, however, lower than the corresponding values given by the true β -oxime melting at 138° (Table V).

We were unable to get α -forms of cinnamaldoxime and furfuraldoxime.

EXPERIMENTAL

The isomeric forms of oximes were purified by crystallisation from alcohol or benzene. Sulphur dioxide, prepared from copper and pure sulphuric acid and bubbled through pure sulphuric acid, was passed through a cool coil condenser and was collected in a receiver protected from atmospheric moisture and surrounded by a freezing mixture. A small conductivity-cell was filled with this solvent up to 5 c.c. mark and was surrounded by freezing mixture kept in a small thermos. The temperature could be maintained at -18° without much difficulty for a period of about 40 minutes which was sufficient for taking three or four conductivity measurements at different dilutions. The cell constant was obtained by determining resistances of solutions of potassium iodide in liquid sulphur dioxide at different dilutions and from the curve plotted from values of molecular conductivities observed by Franklin for such solutions (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1911, 15, 675).

To minimise errors, specific conductivity of liquid sulphur dioxide was determined in each experiment and this was subtracted from the specific conductivity of solution to get specific conductivity of the solute. Different dilutions were obtained by adding small quantities of oxime to the solvent.

TABLE I

<i>Benzaldoximes</i>				<i>Benzaldoximes</i>			
α -Form (b. p. $104^\circ/6$ mm.)				β -Form (m.p. 128° .)			
Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. Condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.	Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.
0.0874 g.	6.923 c.c.	2.77	1.918	0.0368 g.	16.44 c.c.	12.97	21.33
0.1157	5.230	5.08	2.657	0.0745	8.121	16.82	13.66
0.1238	*4.889	6.00	*2.907	0.1265	*4.783	22.14	*16.59

TABLE II

o-Nitrobenzaldoximes

α -Form (m.p. 104°)				β -Form (m.p. 148°)			
Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.	Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.
0.0430 g.	19.31 c.c.	2.70	5.212	0.0255 g.	32.56 c.c.	7.037	22.91
0.0911	*9.111	5.70	*5.194	0.0556	14.93	13.80	20.60
0.0994	8.35	7.10	5.929	0.0658	12.62	18.83	23.75
...	0.0868	*9.563	24.07	*23.01

TABLE III

m-Nitrobenzaldoximes

α -Form (m.p. 121°)				β -Form (changes into α before melting).			
Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>).	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.	Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.
0.0661 g.	The specific conductivity is almost equal to that of the solvent itself.			0.0425 g.	19.53 c.c.	1.853	3.619
0.1291				0.1016	8.190 „	3.761	3.073
0.1747				0.1691	4.908 „	7.090	3.479

TABLE IV

p-Nitrobenzaldoximes

α -Form (m.p. 129°)				β -Form (m.p. 182°)			
Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.	Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.
0.0098 g.	84.70 c.c.	0.506	4.286	0.0140 g.	59.29 c.c.	3.044	18.05
0.0236	35.18	2.630	9.251	No more of the substance could be dissolved.			

TABLE V

p-Methoxybenzaldoximes

α -Form (m. p. 60°)				β -Form (m. p. 138°)			
Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.	Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (<i>v</i>) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^2$.
0.0256 g.	*29.99 c.c.	1.299	3.832*	0.0120 g.	62.91 c.c.	4.761	29.95
0.0660	11.44	3.195	3.656	0.0286	*26.39	9.66	25.50*
0.1072	7.042	4.440	3.127	0.0440	17.16	15.45	26.51
α -Form (m. p. 48°)							
0.0254	29.73	8.93	26.55				
0.0592	12.76	13.70	17.47				
0.0936	8.048	20.53	16.52				

TABLE VI

Furfuraldoximes β -Form (m. p. 92°)

Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (v) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^3$.
0.0296 c.c.	18.75 c.c.	20.22	37.92
0.0986	5.628	48.81	27.48

TABLE VII

Cinnamaldoximes β -Form (m. p. 136°)

Wt. of oxime in 5 c.c.	Dilution (v) $\times 10^{-3}$.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Molar condy. $\times 10^3$.
0.0280 g.	26.25 c.c.	8.49	30.91
0.0736	9.986	13.33	7.491
0.0964	7.625	16.93	4.503

DISCUSSION

Brady and Goldschmidt (*loc. cit.*) commenting on the doubt cast upon Hantzsch's original formulation of aldoximes (*Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 13) observe:—

"On the other hand if the principle applied by Ostwald (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1892, **9**, 553) to the acids of ethylene series, that in an acid the proximity of a so-called 'acidic' group tends to increase the dissociation constant of the acid, can be applied to aldoximes, the benzaldoxime of the *anti*-type where the negative phenyl group is vicinal to the aldoximino hydroxyl group should have a higher dissociation constant than the *syn*-isomeride in which the two groups are further apart".

Since they found indirectly that the α -oximes have a higher dissociation constant, the α -forms are '*anti*' and the β -forms are '*syn*' in agreement with Hantzsch's original configuration. But since we find by direct measurements that the β -forms have a higher conductivity and, therefore, a higher dissociation constant than the α -forms, the β -forms must be '*anti*' and the α -forms '*syn*'. These configurations are reverse of those of Hantzsch's but they are in agreement with those proposed on experimental evidence by Beckmann (*Ber.*, 1923, **56**, 341) and Meisenheimer (*Annalen*, 1926, **446**, 205).